
Methods of evaluation of ethics education in the medical curriculum and their relevance for program development: a scoping review protocol

Authors

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Abstract

Objective: The objective of this scoping review is to explore and map the evaluation methods used for medical ethics education in medical curricula of higher education institutions. We will investigate their aims, research questions, evaluation approaches, including epistemology, research designs and methods used, and how these evaluations contribute to the development and/or improvement of ethics education programs.

Introduction: Ethics education is an important element of the medical curriculum. To ensure the quality of educational programs and improvement of these programs, evaluation is essential. However, little is understood about the evaluation of ethics education in the medical curriculum, which is reflected by a lack of comprehensive reviews on the used evaluation methods. This review seeks to address this gap by exploring current evaluation practices and their impact on program development.

In- and exclusion criteria: This scoping review will include studies of which the focus is the evaluation of medical ethics education and whose participant population consists at least of undergraduate and graduate medical students within medical curricula. Studies focusing on other aspects of medical education than ethics, studies about research integrity and research ethics, studies about professionalism alone, studies concerning ethics education during postgraduate and professional training, studies concerning ethics education in nursing or dentistry, and studies conducted outside of higher education facilities will be excluded.

Methods: Medline, Embase, ERIC, Web of Science Core Collection, and Scopus will be searched for suitable studies. The study selection process involves screening titles and abstracts by two independent reviewers. ASReview will be used during this step. This is followed by full-text assessment by two independent reviewers. A sample will be assessed by two other authors, independently. Data will be extracted using a tool in Excel designed specifically for this review, covering study characteristics, participant details, context, research questions and aim, evaluation approaches (including epistemology, research design and research methods), outcomes of the evaluation and implications for development and/or improvement of practice. The quality hereof will be assessed by a third reviewer, by checking

a sample of the coded studies. Data will be analysed by means of thematic analysis and descriptive statistics. No noteworthy deviations from the methodology are anticipated.

Expected outputs: The results from the thematic analysis will be presented in a narrative summary form. It will provide an in-depth description of how the themes in the studies relate to the research questions and objectives. The results from the descriptive statistics will be presented in tabular and graphical form.

Introduction

Ethics education is an important element of the medical curriculum. This is endorsed by institutions worldwide, such as the General Medical Council (GMC) in the United Kingdom and the Association of American Medical Colleges (AAMC) in the United States, who state that ethics education should be part of the curriculum (General Medical Council, 2018; Obeso et al., 2017). In the Netherlands, the Netherlands Federation of University Medical Centres (NFU) established competencies regarding medical ethics that all doctors in training must obtain before graduation (van de Pol et al., 2020). These competencies guide the development of all medical curricula in the country. They are of vital importance to ensure that future doctors are equipped not only with clinical skills, but also with the necessary ethical knowledge, skills and attitude, to navigate the moral complexities inherent to their jobs.

An important element of education is its evaluation; it gives insight into the effect, quality or added value of an educational program (Cook, 2010; Goldie, 2006; Moreau & Eady, 2023). However, there is a great variety in purposes of evaluation. Chelimsky and Shadish (1997) identified three categories of purposes for evaluation: for accountability, for knowledge and for development. These correspond with a more recent categorization of evaluation within graduate medical education in which an instrumental use (implementing actions based on evaluation findings to improve education), a conceptual use (to enhance the understanding of a program based on evaluation findings) and a symbolic use (to meet reporting requirements or to justify previous actions) are distinguished (Moreau & Eady, 2023). Goldie (2006) stresses the link between evaluation and development of the program, and Cook (2010) emphasizes that an evaluation supports in determining the value of the educational program. Frye and Hemmer (2012) state in the AMEE guide about program evaluation models and related theory, that important aims of evaluation within the field of health professions education (HPE) are *'monitoring and improving the quality and effectiveness of the program'*. It becomes clear that there are multiple purposes of evaluation, and in order to value the evaluation outcomes, the purpose of the evaluation must be clear.

Although literature about medical ethics education is expanding, literature about the evaluation of ethics education is scarce. In their scoping review about teaching and assessment modalities of medical ethics education in the undergraduate curriculum, Souza and Vaswani (2020) concluded that there is a gap in the evaluation of the long-term effectiveness, and that only a small part of educational programs evaluated its practical application. They note that while there is an interest in the contents and delivery of ethics education, there is not as much focus on how the programs are evaluated and what outcomes they have achieved. The same has been identified by Ignatowicz et al. (2023) regarding the effectiveness of interventions used to improve clinical decision making. Wong et al. (2022) conclude their comprehensive systematic scoping review with recommendations for ethics education in practice, but it remains unknown how to evaluate these programs, or what the purpose or aim of the evaluation should be. Some direction regarding the evaluation of ethics education in the

medical curriculum can be found by looking at specific evaluation methods, e.g. the process evaluation of Goldie et al. (2000), or the review about qualitative evaluation methods used in ethics education in general by Watts et al. (2017). Yet before making use of these sources, one must know which questions to ask, and what evaluation approaches are suitable to answer these questions.

The AMEE Guide of Frye and Hemmer (2012) shows that besides different aims of evaluation, different perspectives exist on educational evaluation, leading to different evaluation approaches. Regarding epistemology, they hypothesize that an underlying reductionist perspective tends to encourage the use of a (quasi-) experimental design, whereas a constructivist perspective favours qualitative research methods. They observe a shift from a reductionist view on evaluation, focusing solely on the effectiveness on the program, towards a desire to understand education from the broader perspectives of system theory and complexity theory within the field of HPE. The same shift has been identified by Haji et al. (2013). With regard to medical ethics Gillis et al. (2020) believe that medical ethics and medical humanities will benefit from connecting to the (dominant) methods used in the field of HPE; making more use of quantitative and mixed methods approaches, while Watts et al. (2017) concluded that qualitative methods are used less than quantitative methods in research on ethics education in sciences. From their expertise in scholarship within HPE, Cleland et al. (2021) notice that beginning scholars in education tend to use methodologies for the evaluation of their education that they are familiar with in their research. These contrary views raises the question if the shift that is described by Frye and Hemmer (2012), also occurred within the evaluation of ethics education. Where does the field of evaluation of ethics education in the medical curriculum stands? Are the purposes of the evaluation clear, and what kind of questions are being asked? Is the field also shifting from a more reductionist view (and methodology) towards a constructivist view, or does the field benefit from a shift the other way around? Insight into these aspects of evaluation makes it possible to identify gaps in the (evaluation) literature, and to emphasize which questions should be asked to generate valuable outcomes and to mature/professionalize the field of the evaluation of ethics education, and therefore ethics education itself.

Currently, there is no comprehensive overview of evaluation methods used in medical ethics education, its general aims, or prevalent evaluation approaches in this context. Additionally, it is not well understood how information gained from evaluation processes is used to make recommendations for the development and improvement of medical ethics education in practice. This gap in knowledge makes it challenging to identify best practices of evaluation and areas in need of improvement. If (quasi)-experimental designs are used relatively frequently, there is knowledge about the effectiveness of a program, but it does not provide insight into why or how a program works. The opposite is true for designs with a focus on qualitative methodology. Given the emerging nature of the topic and the scarcity of literature regarding the evaluation of ethics education specifically within the medical curriculum, as well as the need to analyze this knowledge gap, it was decided that a scoping review is the most appropriate method for this study. With a scoping review, it is possible to map the available literature, and to identify the underlying key concepts and gaps in the literature (Tricco et al., 2016).

The objective of this scoping review is to shed light on the evaluation methods used for medical ethics education and to investigate their aims and evaluation approach, including epistemology, research design and methodology. Additionally, we hope to elucidate how elements of evaluation methods are related to the practical development and improvement of

ethics education. A preliminary search of PubMed and ERIC was conducted and no current or underway systematic reviews or scoping reviews on the topic were identified.

Review question

The primary research question guiding this scoping review is:

Which methods of evaluation are used to evaluate ethics education in the medical curriculum, and how does the method of evaluation relate to the development and/or improvement of ethics education?

To comprehensively address the primary question, the following sub questions were formulated:

- What is the aim, research question and the evaluation approach (including epistemology, research design and methodology) and [how] do these align?
- What are the outcomes of the evaluation and how do they relate to the development and/or improvement of the evaluated education?

Keywords

Medical Ethics Education; Educational Evaluation; Evaluation approach; Epistemology; Medical Curriculum; Moral Development; Program Development.

Eligibility criteria

PARTICIPANTS

This scoping review focusses on the evaluation of formal medical ethics education in the undergraduate and graduate level. Studies of which the participants are medical students (undergraduates and graduates during the internships) who have enjoyed medical ethics education during their undergraduate/graduate training will be included. Studies that include medical ethics educators or other stakeholders alongside students to provide different perspectives on the evaluation of medical ethics education are also eligible for inclusion.

Studies concerning graduate level medical students doing a PhD, and of which training within PhD is topic of the evaluation, are excluded. Studies concerning ethics education within postgraduate and professional training will be excluded as well. Because this review aims to get an overview of evaluation approaches used in which students are subject of the evaluation, studies that include medical ethics educators solely, or studies with participants who are not directly related to medical ethics education (e.g. general education staff, hospital personnel, non-medical students) will be excluded.

CONCEPT

The concept of interest is the evaluation methods used for medical ethics education. This includes the aims, research questions, evaluation approaches (including epistemology, research design and methodology), outcomes and the way these evaluations relate to the development and/or improvement of the evaluated educational program.

Studies that only focus on other aspects than the evaluation of medical ethics education, such as clinical skills, medical knowledge, the content and delivery of ethics education, or non-medical ethics education will be excluded. Also, studies that do include evaluations but not

directly related to medical ethics education will be excluded. Studies concerning research integrity, research ethics and professional development in general, will be excluded.

CONTEXT

This review focuses on the context of medical ethics education within higher education institutions. Studies that focus specifically on either a bachelor's/undergraduates or master's/graduates curriculum will be included.

Studies that were conducted outside of higher education facilities will be excluded. Studies with a focus on primary or secondary education or vocational training, or studies that were conducted in non-formal education settings will be excluded. Studies within Nursing or Dentistry will be excluded.

TYPES OF SOURCES

This scoping review considers a broad range of evaluation methods, including qualitative, quantitative and mixed methods research. Studies that are included regarding qualitative approaches are e.g. case studies, grounded theory, phenomenology, ethnography and action research. Regarding quantitative approaches both experimental and quasi-experimental study designs are included, depending on the research question; this includes randomized-controlled trials, non-randomized controlled trials and before and after studies. Additionally, analytical observational studies, including prospective and retrospective cohort studies, case-control studies, and analytical cross-sectional studies, will be considered for inclusion. Descriptive observational study designs, such as case series and descriptive cross-sectional studies, will also be considered for inclusion. Opinion papers, commentaries and reviews will not be considered for inclusion in this scoping review.

Methods

The proposed scoping review will be conducted in accordance with the JBI methodology for scoping reviews (Peters et al., 2020).

SEARCH STRATEGY

A comprehensive search will be performed in the bibliographic databases Medline (Ovid), Embase.com, Eric (Ebsco), Web of Science Core Collection and Scopus, in collaboration with a medical librarian. Search terms will include controlled terms as well as free text terms. The following terms will be used (including synonyms and closely related words) as index terms or free-text words: 'ethics' and 'curriculum' and 'medical education'. The search will be performed without a language restriction. The date will be restricted to studies published between 2010-2025. The reference list of all included sources of evidence will be screened for additional studies.

Studies published in English and Dutch will be included. Although part of the search, publications in other languages will be excluded due to the research team's limited proficiency in other languages. This will ensure accurate data extraction and interpretation.. We have chosen not to restrict to language in the search in order to obtain a comprehensive overview of all available research in the field. Publication date is an exclusion factor, because this review aims to give an overview of current evaluation practices. Studies published before 2010 will be excluded. The final search in Medline is included as Appendix 1.

STUDY/SOURCE OF EVIDENCE SELECTION

Following the search, duplicates will be removed. A selection of identified citations will be uploaded into Rayyan (Ouzzani et al., 2016). In a pilot test, titles and abstracts of 50-100 articles will then be screened by two reviewers independently for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the review, to ensure inter-rater agreement of 70-80% (Tricco et al., 2018). When there is disagreement between the two reviewers, a third reviewer will be included.

After the pilot, all titles and abstracts will be screened by two authors independently, using ASReview (Van De Schoot et al., 2021). ASReview is a tool using machine learning to accelerate the screening process by prioritising the records. Records with the highest probability to be included, will be presented first. The reviewers still decide on whether or not to include the record (Van De Schoot et al., 2021). The reviewers do not have to screen all the records, because at a certain point only irrelevant records will be shown. The SAFE procedure describes how to determine when screening can be stopped (Boetje & van de Schoot, 2024). This guideline will be combined with existing quality checks on conducting scoping reviews like the JBI guideline and PRISMA-ScR (Peters et al., 2020; Tricco et al., 2018). Both reviewers will start with the same prior knowledge in ASReview, but then train their own model. Disagreements will be solved by consensus or a third reviewer. Following the SAFE procedure (phase 3 and 4), an additional test will be done on the unlabelled and irrelevant records.

Potentially relevant resources will be retrieved in full and their citation details imported into Rayyan. The full text will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by two reviewers independently. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence at full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded in the data extraction tool (Excel) and reported in the scoping review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final scoping review and presented in a Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses extension for scoping review (PRISMA-ScR) flow diagram (Tricco et al., 2018).

DATA EXTRACTION

Data from the included papers will be extracted by two reviewers independently. They will use a data tool in Excel developed specifically for this purpose. The tool will be tested and refined to ensure that it includes all relevant data. The data extraction process will involve the following steps:

- 1) Development of the data extraction tool: the tool will be developed keeping the original review questions and objectives in mind. Its design will include fields for:
 - a. Study characteristics (e.g. authors, country, year of publication, etc.)
 - b. Participant details (e.g. number, demographics)
 - c. Context (e.g. educational setting, curriculum type, stage in education)
 - d. Aim and research question
 - e. Evaluation approach (i.e. epistemology, research design and methodology) and their alignment with d.
 - f. Outcomes of evaluation
 - g. Impact on further development and/or improvement of the evaluated program
 If there is any missing data, authors from the included studies will be contacted.

- 2) Testing of the data extraction tool: the two reviewers will test the tool with a sample of 5 studies to identify if there are gaps or areas in need of improvement. Results of the testing-phase will be discussed with the other authors and used to improve the tool further.
- 3) Data extraction process: two reviewers will use the developed data extraction tool to extract data from all the included studies independently.
- 4) Consistency and accuracy: to ensure the data is handled consistently and accurately, the reviewers will hold regular meetings. Any disagreements regarding the extraction process will be solved by discussion. An additional independent reviewer will be included if the two original reviewers cannot reach consensus.
- 5) Quality check: two other authors will review the extracted data to ensure accuracy. Mistakes/inconsistencies will be solved through revision and discussion among the reviewers.

A draft extraction form is provided (see Appendix 2). The draft data extraction tool will be modified and revised as necessary during the process of extracting data from each included evidence source. Modifications will be detailed in the scoping review.

DATA ANALYSIS AND PRESENTATION

We will combine thematic analysis and descriptive statistics to analyze and present the data in this scoping review.

Thematic Analysis

- 1) We will create a coding framework in advance to systematically identify and code recurring themes in the included studies. The framework will be based on a preliminary set of codes that is derived from the review's research questions and objectives and will be developed as we go. We will pilot the coding framework using a sample of studies to ensure that it includes all relevant themes.
- 2) Using this coding framework, two reviewers will independently code all the included studies. This process involves reading the studies thoroughly while marking sections of the text that match the predefined codes. Disagreements between the two reviewers will be solved through discussion or, if discussion cannot resolve the disagreement, the involvement of a third independent reviewer. Coding will be checked by one of the other authors.
- 3) We will write a detailed account of the findings from each study for each identified theme. This includes:
 - a. A description of the theme and its relevance to the evaluation of medical ethics education
 - b. A detailed description of the results from each study concerning this theme
 - c. An analysis of similarities/differences between the included studies

Descriptive statistics

- 1) We will make use of descriptive statistics to quantify the characteristics of the included studies, including:
 - a. Study characteristics: e.g. year of publication, country, etc.
 - b. Participant details: e.g. number of participants, demographics,
 - c. Context: e.g. educational setting (e.g. educational setting, curriculum type, stage in education)
 - d. Aim and research question
 - e. Evaluation approach: e.g. epistemology, research design and methodology
 - f. Outcomes
 - g. Impact on further development and/or improvement of the evaluated program

- 2) By quantifying these characteristics we hope to identify any trends and shifts in the literature over time, differences between regions, and epistemological shifts (e.g. positivist -> constructivist)

The results from the thematic analysis will be presented in a narrative summary form (mostly textual). It will provide an in-depth description of how the themes in the studies relate to the research questions and objectives. We aim to also include reflections of how these themes impact the development and/or improvement of medical ethics education programs.

The results from the descriptive statistics will be presented in tabular and graphical form. Tables are well-suited to summarize the included studies' characteristics, whereas graphs and charts can depict any trends/shifts.

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Conflicts of interest

There is no conflict of interest in this project.

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Appendices

APPENDIX I: SEARCH STRATEGY MEDLINE

Search	Query Medline (Ovid) – January 27, 2025	Results
#1	Exp Education/ OR exp Models, Educational/ OR (education* OR teach* OR training* OR course* OR curriculum OR workshop*).ti,ab,kf	2,686,649
#2	Exp Education, Medical/ OR exp Students, Medical/ OR ((medical OR medicine OR health* OR clinic*) ADJ2 (education OR school* OR student*)).ti,ab,kf	392,115

Search	Query Medline (Ovid) – January 27, 2025	Results
#3	Ethics/ OR exp Bioethics/ OR exp Bioethical Issues/ OR exp Ethical Analysis/ OR exp Ethics, Professional/ OR exp Ethics, Medical/ OR exp Moral Development/ OR (ethic* OR bioethic* OR (moral ADJ2 (reasoning OR sensitivity OR argumentation OR judgment OR development OR skill*))).ti,ab,kf	244,867
#4	Exp Program Evaluation/ OR "Evaluation Study".pt OR exp Evaluation Studies as Topic/ OR (evaluat* OR assess* OR impact* OR effect*).ti,ab,kf	15,375,784
#5	1 AND 2 AND 3 AND 4	5,687
#6	5 and 2010:2026.(sa_year).	4,344

APPENDIX II: DRAFT DATA EXTRACTION INSTRUMENT

Study characteristics	
Authors	
Title	
Journal	
Year of publication	
Country	
Participant details	
Number of participants	
Age range	
Context	
Educational setting	(e.g. course, lecture, working group, assessment)
Curriculum type/educational level	(i.e. undergraduate/graduate)
Stage in education	(e.g. year)
Aim & research question	
Aim	
Research question	
Evaluation approach	
Epistemology/ research paradigm	(e.g. constructivist/positivist)
Research design	(e.g. experimental, descriptive, observational)
Methodology	
Timing of evaluation	(e.g. throughout a course, at the end)
Alignment with aim and RQ	
Outcomes	
Key findings	(e.g. which moral competences, what has changed, etc.)
Impact on program development	